

Mixed Metal Complexes of some Tetradentate Bifunctional Schiff Bases

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Metal and mixed metal complexes of bifunctional salicylidene-*m*-(and -*p*-)phenylenediamine have been studied spectrophotometrically. The ligands form 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 (M(II) : L) metal complexes. The colour of the complexes containing two different metal ions is much deeper than that of the corresponding mononuclear complexes of these metal ions. This confirms the formation of mixed metal complexes. The stoichiometry and stability of the complexes have been evaluated in solution by using spectrophotometric methods. Elemental analysis, conductometric measurements, electronic and ir spectra have been used for identification of the solid complexes.

THE bifunctional Schiff bases have received much attention for their analytical application. This class of compounds have two possible coordination sites, namely, two azomethine and two hydroxyl groups. This provides the possibility of forming 1 : 1 and/or 2 : 1 (M(II) : L) chelates.

In spite of the vast amount of reports on the study of mixed metal complexes of the bifunctional Schiff bases derived from *o*-diamines¹⁻⁵, detailed study on those complexes which are derived from *meta*- and *para*-phenylenediamines have not been carried out. So, the present study was aimed to investigate the metal and mixed metal chelates of divalent metal ions (Cu, Co, Ni and Mn) with *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)-*m*-phenylenediamine (H₂A) and *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine (H₂B). The study involves the effects of the secondary metal ions on the stabilities of the binary complexes. Stoichiometry and stability have been determined spectrophotometrically. The ir spectra of the solid chelates are also reported and discussed.

Experimental

Reagents of analytical quality (Merck or B.D.H.) were used. The ligands H₂A and H₂B were prepared by refluxing the corresponding phenylenediamine and salicylaldehyde (in 1 : 2 ratio) in absolute ethanol. The solid product was filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds were characterised by ir spectra and elemental analysis.

Preparation of complexes: The binary complexes were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solutions of the Schiff base (H₂A/H₂B) and the metal salts (CuCl₂·6H₂O, CoCl₂·6H₂O, NiCl₂·6H₂O and MnCl₂·4H₂O) for ~1 h. The mixture was concentrated to half the volume and left to cool. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried. The homobinuclear complexes

was prepared similarly but by adding the ethanolic solution of the metal ion to that containing an equimolecular amount of the binary complex having the same metal ion.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing two different metal ions (one of them being Cu^{II} with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II} and the other being Ni^{II} with Mn^{II}) were prepared by the reaction of binary complex solution with an equimolecular amount of the other metal ion. The mixture was stirred for ~0.5 h and then refluxed for 2-3 h. The separated complex was filtered as described before. The structures of the solid complexes were confirmed by ir spectra and elemental analysis. In heterobinuclear complexes, the metal ions were determined iodometrically after the complex had been decomposed by hot concentrated nitric acid⁶. The data obtained are listed in Table 1.

Preparation of solutions: Stock solutions of the bifunctional Schiff bases and the metal salts (1×10⁻² mol dm⁻³) were prepared by dissolving each in absolute ethanol. In case of H₂B compound dioxane was used as a solvent due to its low soluble character in ethanol. Solutions of metal ions were standardised using conventional procedures⁷. A 1×10⁻² mol dm⁻³ stock solution of each of the isolated complexes in DMF was prepared for molar conductance measurements.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu uv-240 spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells. Molar conductance measurements were performed in DMF at 25° using a Pye conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) show that the complexes have metal:

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE (Λ_M , $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Mol.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Λ_m	ν_{\max} (cm^{-1})		
		C	N	Cl	M	M'		ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$
H₂A—chelates										
CuA	375.9	64.2 (63.4)	7.4 (7.5)	—	17.1 (16.9)	—	5.7	—	1 622s 1 613m	1 284m 1 285
(Cu) ₂ A.Cl ₂	510.3	47.1 (47.1)	5.5 (5.5)	14.1 (13.9)	24.6 (24.4)	—	4.3	—	1 615	1 292
NiA	371.1	65.0 (64.7)	7.4 (7.6)	—	16.0 (15.8)	—	5.4	—	1 614	1 284
(Ni) ₂ A.Cl ₂	500.7	47.8 (48.0)	5.5 (5.6)	14.1 (14.2)	23.8 (23.5)	—	5.1	—	1 610	1 290
(Co) ₂ A.Cl ₂	501.1	48.3 (47.9)	5.7 (5.6)	14.1 (14.1)	23.4 (23.5)	—	4.3	—	1 612	1 288
(Mn) ₂ A.Cl ₂	493.1	48.8 (48.7)	5.9 (5.7)	14.2 (14.4)	22.2 (22.3)	—	4.0	—	1 610	1 285
Cu/Ni ACl ₂	505.5	47.7 (47.5)	5.5 (5.5)	13.8 (14.0)	12.9 (12.6)	11.4 (11.6)	5.2	—	1 590	1 325
Cu/Co ACl ₂	505.7	47.4 (47.5)	5.6 (5.5)	13.9 (14.0)	12.8 (12.6)	11.5 (11.6)	4.8	—	1 592	1 322
Ni/Mn ACl ₂	501.7	47.7 (47.9)	5.5 (5.6)	14.0 (14.1)	12.5 (12.7)	10.7 (11.0)	4.7	—	1 595	1 315
Ni/Mn ACl ₂	496.9	48.2 (48.3)	5.6 (5.6)	14.2 (14.3)	12.1 (11.8)	11.0 (11.1)	4.8	—	1 600	1 300
H₂B—chelates										
CuHBCl.H ₂ O	430.4	55.8 (55.8)	6.4 (6.5)	8.0 (8.2)	14.7 (14.8)	—	3.4	3 420b	1 628 s 1 620	1 282s 1 294
(Cu) ₂ BCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	546.4	43.9 (44.0)	4.9 (5.1)	12.9 (13.0)	23.0 (23.3)	—	3.2	3 440b	1 618m	1 330
(Ni) ₂ BCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	536.7	44.5 (44.8)	5.2 (5.2)	13.1 (13.2)	22.2 (21.9)	—	3.0	3 400b	1 620	1 304
CoHBCl.H ₂ O	425.8	56.6 (56.4)	6.4 (6.6)	8.4 (8.3)	14.1 (13.8)	—	3.8	3 320b	1 615	1 290
MnHBCl.H ₂ O	421.8	56.9 (57.0)	6.7 (6.6)	8.4 (8.4)	12.9 (13.0)	—	2.6	3 320b	1 622m	1 286
CuNiBCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	541.5	44.3 (44.4)	5.1 (5.2)	13.3 (13.1)	11.5 (11.7)	11.0 (10.8)	2.9	3 345b	1 590	1 340
CuCoBCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	541.8	44.3 (44.3)	5.2 (5.2)	13.0 (13.1)	11.6 (11.7)	11.0 (10.9)	2.1	3 340	1 600	1 332
NiMnBCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	532.9	45.0 (45.1)	5.2 (5.3)	13.5 (13.3)	11.3 (11.3)	10.9 (10.3)	1.9	3 350	1 612	1 310

ligand stoichiometry of 2 : 1 and 1 : 1. The possible structures suggested for H₂B complexes are MM'BCl₂(H₂O), MHBCl.H₂O and that for H₂A complexes are MAM'Cl₂, MA, where M and M' represent the same metal ion in case of homobinuclear complexes or different metal ions in case of heterobinuclear complexes (M or M' = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II}).

The molar conductance values of 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solutions of the solid complexes in DMF (Table 1) were found in the range 1.9–5.7 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, which indicate their non-electrolytic nature⁸. On the other hand, the binary complexes show slightly higher molar conductance than the homo- or heterobinuclear complexes. This behaviour may be due to solvolysis of the covalent chloride in the latter complexes.

The observed important frequencies together with the approximate assignments are listed in Table 1. The ir data of the free ligands do not have a clear ν_{OH} band. This is due to the expected involvement of the OH groups in strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The H₂B com-

plexes show a broad band at 3 350–3 440 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of coordinated water in the complexes⁹. The bands at 1 622 (H₂A) and 1 628 cm⁻¹ (H₂B) of the ligands may be assigned to azomethines $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. This band is shifted slightly towards lower frequency on complexation, which clearly indicates the involvement of the two azomethine nitrogen atoms on complexation. In case of homo- and heterobinuclear complexes, the lower frequency shifts of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ is more pronounced than that for the binary complexes. In the free ligands, the strong band at $\sim 1 282 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to phenolic $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ mode¹⁰. The high frequency shift of this band on complexation suggests that the oxygen atoms of the phenolic groups are one of the bonding sites of the ligands. In mixed metal complexes the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band shifted to higher frequencies relative to its position in the binary metal complexes. This may be due to the higher mesomeric interaction occurring within the chelated rings. The mesomeric interaction can be explained on the basis of formation of partial positive charge on the nitrogen atoms of C=N group and negative one on the oxygen atoms as a result of metal-ligand linkage.

The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit several bands in the region 442–508 cm^{-1} assigned to metal-ligand stretching vibrations. This assignment is based on the assumption that there are some degree of coupling between $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ modes^{1,2}.

Based on the above results of elemental analysis and ir spectra, the structural formula of the 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) chelates of H_2A and H_2B can be represented by structures 1 and 2 respectively.

Electronic spectra: The spectra of ethanolic solutions of the free ligands have definite absorption band at 370 (H_2A) and 340 nm (H_2B) assigned to intramolecular CT transition^{1,2}. On complexation, this band suffers a red-shift (Fig. 1). The newly formed band can be assigned to metal to

Fig. 1. Visible spectra of 4×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} H_2B ligand (a) with 4×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} (a) Cu^{II} , (b) Ni^{II} , (c) Co^{II} , (d) Mn^{II} ; 1 : 1 : 1 ratio of H_2B with (f) $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, (g) $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, (h) $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ and (k) $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$.

ligand CT transition from the occupied metal d orbitals to low energy ligand π^* orbitals. A higher red-shift is observed for solutions containing 1 : 1 metal-ligand complexes and another mole of metal ion of the same or different type. The latter shift is presumably due to the formation of homo- or

heterobinuclear complex species. The maximum colour development for 2 : 1 metal to H_2A complexes is attained after ~ 1 h at room temperature. The magnitude of the lower energy shift of the ligand CT band, on complexation with the different metal ions studied, follows the order : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ and in the case of heterobinuclear complexes : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$. This behaviour suggests that the stability of the complex is expected to decrease in the above direction.

The stoichiometry of the different complexes liable to form in solution has been determined by the widely used spectrophotometric mole-ratio and continuous variation methods^{13,14}. In the case of heterobinuclear system, the molar fraction of the two components were varied continuously and the third component is kept constant for all solutions in the series. Under such conditions the ternary system is modified to a quasi-binary one. The spectra of the reaction mixture were recorded using a reagent blank. Representative results are given in Figs. 2 and 3.

Fig. 2. Continuous variation plots.

Fig. 3. molar ratio plots.

For heterobinuclear complexes of H_2B with (a) Mn/Ni , (b) Cu/Mn , (c) Cu/Co , (d) Cu/Ni ; and of H_2A with (e) Cu/Ni , (f) Cu/Co , (g) Cu/Mn and (h) Ni/Mn ; $[\text{M}] + [\text{M}'] + [\text{L}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} .

TABLE 2—MEAN FORMATION CONSTANTS ($\log K_f$, $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) AND UV SPECTRAL (λ_{max} , nm, ϵ_{max} , $\times 10^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) DATA OF COMPLEXES AT 27°

M(II)	M(II) : L ratio	Complexes with H ₂ A			Complexes with H ₂ B		
		$\log K_f$	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	$\log K_f$	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}
CuII	1 : 1	5.28	525	16.6	6.18	492	22.0
	2 : 1	10.26	525	12.0	11.74	492	8.1
NiII	1 : 1	4.88	460	6.7	5.57	480	23.7
	2 : 1	9.94	460	5.3	11.18	480	9.8
CoII	1 : 1	4.49	438	7.0	4.96	460	23.0
	2 : 1	9.15	438	5.4	—	—	—
MnII	1 : 1	3.89	402	4.2	4.18	446	8.8
	2 : 1	7.85	402	3.7	—	—	—
CuII/NiII	1 : 1 : 1	10.17	658	10.9	11.87	670	12.0
CuII/CoII	1 : 1 : 1	9.85	640	9.3	11.03	667	16.6
CuII/MnII	1 : 1 : 1	9.34	630	10.0	10.34	658	9.1
NiII/MnII	1 : 1 : 1	8.76	505	4.9	10.08	515	10.0

Both the methods revealed 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and/or 1 : 1 : 1 stoichiometry for binary, homo- and heterobinuclear complexes studied.

The validity of Beer's law for the heterobinuclear systems are examined. The process is carried out by taking a large fixed concentration of the 1 : 1 complex and varying concentrations of the other metal ions. The absorbance values of such solutions of the 1 : 1 : 1 system were measured against a reagent blank. This method affords a new means for the rapid microdetermination of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} ions up to 8.93, 7.04 and 4.47 ppm level respectively. The high reproducibility of the method is indicated by the low standard deviation values (~ 0.008) and high absorptivities (Table 2).

Apparent formation constants: The formation constants (K_f) of the binary complexes were determined from the results of the mole-ratio and continuous variation methods¹⁵. For the heterobinuclear complexes, the formation constants were calculated in a manner similar to that described for the 1 : 1 metal-ligand complex. The following equations are used :

If C is the initial concentration of each metal ion, A_m the limiting absorbance corresponding to the concentration of $MM'L$ at full colour development and A the concentration of $MM'L$ existing in equilibrium, then at equilibrium,

$$[MM'L] = C(A/A_m); [M] = [M'] = [L] = C(1 - A/A_m)$$

Then, $K_f = [MM'L]/[M][M'][L]$
 $= (A/A_m)/C^2(1 - A/A_m)^3$

The K_f values obtained for the different complexes are listed in Table 2. The results reveal the following facts. (i) The $\log K_f$ values of the same metal complex with H₂A ligand are in general lower than that of the H₂B complexes. This is due to the effect of hindrance as a result of binuclear nature of H₂A complexes (structures 1 and 2). On the other hand, the four-coordinating groups of H₂B ligand cannot attach to a single ion. Thus, the formed complexes are expected to have a planar

structure. (ii) The $\log K_f$ values of the same ligand run in the same direction with the red-shift in λ_{max} of the CT band as shown above. This is in agreement with the general order of stability of these metal ion complexes^{16,17}. Generally, the 1 : 1 binary complex stabilities are lower than those of the homo- or heterobinuclear complex. This is because more coordination sites are normally available for binding the second metal ion. Evidently $\Delta \log K$ ($\log K_{\text{MM'L}} - \log K_{\text{ML}}$) values are positive for all systems under study. This confirms that the binuclear systems are stabler than the binary systems. Further, the constancy of $\Delta \log K$ values reveals that the stability of binuclear complex is proportional to stability of binary complex¹⁸. (iii) The M-L interaction may be electrostatic since K_f is inversely proportional to metal ion radii¹⁹. Similarly, a linear relationship has been obtained on plotting $\log K_f$ values vs ionisation potential or electronegativity of the metal ions under study. This is expected, since the electron affinity of the metal ion to gain electron from the donor atom increases as the ionisation potential is increased²⁰.

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